

Assessing the Efficacy of Bio-Coagulants in Water Treatment

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ABSTRACT:

The study was designed to investigate the efficacy of Bio-Coagulants in water treatment settling tanks using alum (the commercially available coagulant) as a control for comparison. The study employed the preparation of synthetic turbid water using clay as a source of turbidity, jar tests and settling columns to construct settling curves for evaluating removal efficiencies of the biocoagulants, using standard procedures. The findings of the study revealed significant linear correlation ($R^2 = 0.9967$) between clay suspension dosage (x) and turbidity (y), which enabled the replication of synthetic turbid water of the desired turbidity using clay. The equation representing the relationship was found to be $y = 1.0705x - 9.7131$. From the jar tests, the optimum dosages of the coagulants were 3mg/l, and 8mg/l for M. Oleifera seed extract and watermelon seed extract respectively as coagulants. These dosages resulted in 97 and 91.6% turbidity removal for the respective coagulants. Also, the optimum removal efficiencies observed from the settling column tests were 97%, 84.5% and 70.8% using alum, Moringa oleifera and watermelon seeds, respectively. The study concluded that the plant dimensions designed using alum as coagulant were the most economical followed closely by the one designed using M. Oleifera seed extract (3m width by 37.2m length by 2.5m depth; and 3m wide by 37.8m length by 2.5m depth, respectively). The researcher therefore, recommends that M. Oleifera seed extract could be a viable alternative to alum as a coagulant for use in water treatment settling tanks.

Keywords: M. Oleifera, Water Melon, Bio-Coagulants, Turbidity, Settling Tank.

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INTRODUCTION

Globally, social stability and economic growth are significantly influenced by water. Water conservation and purification have always been the main goals of world politics [5]. Safe water is important for humans, plants and animals. For example, humans need water as a key element in the metabolic process to breakdown large substances into small substances and transport them to other parts of the body. According to Hassan et al. [8], anthropogenic activities including agriculture, illegal waste dumping, sewage effluent discharge, and landfill leachate leakage are the causes of water contamination.

In water treatment, coagulation is an essential process that breaks down suspended particles and reacts with organic compounds in untreated water. The formation of insoluble compounds between organic matter and coagulants, as well as the adsorption on freshly formed hydroxide precipitate, could be the determining method of organic matter removal by coagulation [16].

In order to encourage particle collision and the creation of floccules, coagulants like alum, which are frequently used, lessen the repulsive attraction between particulate matter. These synthetic coagulants have a negative impact on the environment and health, examples, aluminum ion concentrations above 50µg/L are potentially toxic to fish and aquatic organisms, and polyacrylamide

residues (acrylamide) are neurotoxic and poses strong carcinogenic properties which are peripheral nerve toxins that affect man and animals [7].

PRIMARY AND SECONDARY COAGULANTS

The purpose of primary coagulants is to destabilize particles and induce clumping [13]. Metallic salts like ferric sulphate, aluminum sulphate (also known as alum), and ferric chloride are examples of primary coagulants. Primary coagulants can also be made of cationic polymers.

According to Smith [13], floc formation is maintained and slow-settling floc is given density by secondary coagulants or coagulant aids. In conjunction with a primary coagulant, organic polymers like poly-aluminum hydroxy chloride (PACl) are commonly employed to improve coagulation. These organic polymers have the advantage of being much more effective at low dosages and having a high positive charge. Money can be saved because, despite their potential higher cost, they might only require a smaller quantity. Additionally, organic polymers usually produce less sludge.

MORINGA IOLEIFERA ISEED IEXTRACT

M.Oleifera is the most widely cultivated species in the monogeneric family, Moringaceae, i.e. native to the sub-Himalayan regions of India, Pakistan, Bangladesh and Afghanistan [2]. Moringa oleifera is widely grown in the tropics. It is also found in many states in Nigeria. It is sometimes called drumstick or horseradish.

According to Eilert [6], Moringa oleifera seeds contain significant amounts of water-soluble, low molecular weight proteins, which acquire a positive charge when the ground seeds are added to raw water. These proteins attract the predominantly negatively charged particles (such as clay, silt, bacteria) and other toxic particles in water.

M.Oleifera seeds have been used as a primary coagulant in drinking water clarification and wastewater treatment due to the presence of a water-soluble cationic coagulant protein that are capable of reducing the turbidity of raw water [10].

A study carried out by Nand et al, (2019) showed that Moringa seeds were much more effective in water purification in terms of adsorption of metals. The percentage removal by Moringa seeds were 90% for copper, 80% for lead, 60% for cadmium and 50% for zinc and chromium.

The seed has also been found to have antimicrobial activity against bacteria, moulds and fungi [9]. Laboratory analyzes confirm that granules are very effective in removing suspended solids, contributing to their ability to purify water of low or high turbidity [4].

WATERMELON SEED EXTRACT

Watermelon (*Citrullus lanatus* var. *lanatus*) is a species of vine-like flowering plant (scrambler and trailer) in the family Cucurbitaceae. Watermelon seeds have the ability to remove turbidity in water.

When watermelon seed cake is used in combination with a chemical coagulant such as alum, a higher ability to remove color and turbidity is observed, clarifying the color up to 100% [11]. The study further suggested a combined coagulant dosage ratio of 80% watermelon seed powder and 20% alum (ideal for water treatment).

SEDIMENTATION

Sedimentation is a treatment process in which suspended particles, such as flocs, sand and clay, are settled in water and accumulate at the bottom of a settling tank as sludge where the sludge is regularly evacuated. Clean water leaves the settling tank through the collection tank located at the end of the horizontal settling tank or above the vertical settling tank.

This process is usually carried out before application of filters. Sedimentation, coagulation, flocculation and filtration form an integrated solid separation process for water treatment and if there is a shortcoming in any of these segments, there are implications to the segments downstream [8].

Sedimentation, coagulation and flocculation are not rigidly separated and ideally, they contribute to the removal of 90% of the suspended solids, turbidity and colour before filtration [14]. This prevents rapid clogging of sand filters. Sedimentation can remove suspended solids and reduce turbidity by approximately 50 to 90%, depending on the nature of the solids, the degree of pretreatment provided, and the design of the settling tank. Common values are between 60 and 80% [8]. Sedimentation occurs due to the difference in density between suspended particles and water.

The following factors affect the sedimentation process: density, suspended particle size, water temperature; flow stabilization, bed erosion and flocculation [3]. Most suspended solids of concern in water treatment settle according to Stokes' Law:

$$v_s = \frac{(\rho_1 - \rho) d^2}{18\mu} \quad (1)$$

Where v_s = velocity of settlement, g = acceleration of free fall, ρ_1 , = densities of particle and fluid respectively d = diameter of the particle μ = dynamic viscosity of the fluid.

This theory applies to discrete particles, but in settling tanks, hindered settling is what is obtainable.

STUDY AREA

The study was carried out in the Environmental Engineering Laboratory, Department of Water Resources and Environmental Engineering, Ahmadu Bello University Zaria, Nigeria.

PREPARATION OF SYNTHETIC TURBID WATER

- i. The turbid water was prepared using clay in solid form obtained from Hayin Commander Hayin Dogo, Samaru Zaria, Nigeria. The clay was sieved using sieve number 200 (0.075mm) to obtain fine powder after grinding using mortar and pestle.
- ii. About 5g, 10g and 15g respectively of the clay powder were weighed and added to 1000ml of distilled water in a beaker and stirred using a flocculator (Peterson Candy Limited, England) for 5 minutes at 40rpm and then at 200rpm for 25 minutes to achieve a uniform mixing. The suspension was kept for 1hour to settle.
- iii. The suspensions were decanted and diluted with distilled water to achieve the desired turbidity level [1].

Figure 1. Synthetic turbid water

Source: Author

PREPARATION OF ALUM SOLUTION

1. Alum ($Al_2(SO_4)_3$) was obtained in its solid form and was broken down into smaller units using mortar and pestle.
2. Alum solution was prepared by dissolving 1 g of alum in 100ml distilled water.
3. The solution was stirred for 10 minutes at low speed of 40rpm using magnetic stirrer.

PREPARATION OF MORINGA OLEIFERA SEED

Dried *M. Oleifera* seeds were obtained from Samaru market, Zaria. The shells and coats on the seeds were removed manually. The seeds that were shelled was then grinded into a fine powder using a domestic blender (Vitamix 5200). About 2g of grinded *Moringa oleifera* was weighed and dissolved in 100ml of distilled water to make a solution [1]. The solution was stirred using a magnetic stirrer at speed of 40rpm for 5 minutes and at 200rpm for 10 minutes to achieve a uniform mixing and then filter through muslin cloth and Whatman no.1 filter paper.

PREPARATION OF WATERMELON SEED EXTRACT

- i. Dried watermelon seeds were obtained and shelled; the shelled seeds were broken down into smaller units using mortar and pestle.
- ii. A 10g of the finely blended watermelon seeds was used to make a solution by dissolving in a 100ml of distilled water.
- iii. The solution was stirred using a magnetic stirrer at speed of 40rpm for 5 minutes and at 200rpm for 10 minutes to achieve a uniform mixing and then filter through domestic sieve and Whatman no. 1 filter paper.

JAR TEST

Jar tests were carried out by using a jar tester (Phipps and Bird, Model 300) to evaluate coagulation activity at several dose levels of coagulants. Four 500 ml of synthetic beakers filled water were placed in the slots of the jar tester. The synthetic waters were agitated using the flocculator at 100rpm and 10rpm. During this agitation, varying dosage of coagulants (1mg/l to 3mg/l for *M. oleifera*, 1mg/l to 8mg/l for watermelon and 1mg/l to 6mg/l for alum) was added to each beaker and agitated using the flocculator for 2 min at 100 rpm. The speed used for mixing was reduced to 10rpm in 15 minutes using slow mixing. The samples were then removed from the jar tester and allowed to settle undisturbed for 1 hour. After sedimentation for 1 h; about 5 ml of the sample was collected from about 1 cm below the surface of the water and subjected to turbidity measurement using a turbidity meter to obtain the optimum dosage of the coagulant.

Figure 2. Jar test apparatus

Source: Author

COAGULATION AND FLOCCULATION IN SETTLING COLUMN

The optimum dosage of the respective coagulants obtained from the jar tests, were used to evaluate the performance of the coagulants in a settling column. Hence, 120mg of M.Oleifera seed extract was added to 20 litres of synthetic turbid water and agitated using a flocculator for coagulation to take place. The mixture was immediately transferred to a settling column and settled by gravity.

Similar procedure was repeated separately for watermelon seed extract and alum using 320mg and 240mg in 20 litres of synthetic turbid water (101NTU) respectively.

COLUMN SETTLING TANK ANALYSIS

The settling column of diameter 102mm and depth 2m with four sampling ports provided at 0.5 m, 1.0 m, 1.5 m, 2.0m, from the bottom of column was used. The steps involved are as follows;

- i. Fill the settling column with coagulated turbid water of initial turbidity of 150 NTU.
- ii. The sample was then allowed to settle and after time intervals of 20, 40, 60, 80, 100, 120, 140, 160 and 180 min, samples were taken from each sampling port from top to bottom. Turbidity and total suspended solids of each sample were measured using a turbidity meter and balance.

And the results are recorded in the table. The turbidity removal percentage for the collected samples was calculated based on their initial turbidity measurements.

Then the graph of sampling port depth versus time of percentage removal of turbidity readings were plotted. From these plots, the overall removal efficiency was calculated at given time intervals.

Figure 3. Settling Column

Source: Author

DETERMINATION OF TOTAL SUSPENDED SOLIDS (TSS)

TSS was determined for each sample and the percentage removal was calculated:

$$R (\%) = (1 - C_t / C_o) \quad (2)$$

Where R (%) = percentage removal at a given depth and time, %. C_t = concentration at time t , and given depth, mg/l. C_o = initial concentration, mg/l. The procedures to obtain the TSS of the samples are according to the standard method described in ASTM 2540 [15].

DETERMINATION OF TURBIDITY

To obtain the turbidity of the samples, the following procedures were done [15]; 20ml of the sample was collected for determination of turbidity. To ensure samples are within the measurement range of the turbidity meter (HACH, 2100P, by Hach chemical, USA), the samples were appropriately diluted by adding 1ml of the sample to 50ml of distilled water. 10ml of the diluted sample is transferred into a glass cuvette and inserted into the turbidity meter for reading; the value is now multiplied by 50 to obtain the actual turbidity in NTU. Overall turbidity removals are obtained in a similar fashion as in equation 3.1, with turbidities replacing concentrations.

PREPARATION OF SYNTHETIC TURBID WATER

Table 1 shows the proportion of settling and suspended particles in the synthetic turbid water prepared using 5g, 10g, and 15g of the clay in 1000 ml of distilled water. The 15g of the clay was adopted to prepare the synthetic turbid water because it serves the purpose of the type of turbidity (medium turbidity) required in this research [1].

Table 1. Assessing the Settling Properties of the Clay Suspension

Clay (g/l)	Settling Particles (mg/l)	Suspended Particles (mg/l)
5.0	5.0	0.024
10.0	10.0	0.025
15.0	15.0	0.026

Further analysis was performed to determine the relationship between clay suspension dosage and turbidity. The results are presented in table 2 and figure 4.

Table 2. Relationship Between Clay Suspension Dosage and Turbidity

Clay Suspension (%)	100	90	70	60	40	20	10
Distilled Water (%)	0	10	30	40	60	80	90
Turbidity (NTU)	101	85	64	52	33	12	2.5

Table 2 shows that as the clay suspension dosage increased from 10% to 100%, the turbidity of the synthetic turbid water increased from 2.5 NTU to 101 NTU.

From Figure 4 the turbidity of the synthetic turbid water showed a strong linear correlation to the clay suspension dosage, with correlation coefficient (R^2) of 0.9967. this value is indicative of strong positive correlation between the two variables. Thus, this value indicates a strong positive correlation between the two variables.

Figure 4. Regression Plot for Synthetic Turbid Water

DETERMINATION OF OPTIMUM COAGULANT DOSAGES

500ml of the synthetic turbid water was used throughout the jar tests. These tests were carried out in order to determine the optimum dosages of each coagulant, that would be used for the settling test analysis. The optimum dosages correspond to the dosage that produces minimum residual turbidity (optimum turbidity reduction) from the jar tests. These results depict the response of turbidity to dosage and are presented in figure 5 to figure 6.

Figure 5. Regression Plot of Turbidity Against Moringa Seed Extract Dosage

Figure 5 gave an optimum dosage of 3mg/l for *M.Oleifera* seed extract. This dosage was used to treat the synthetic turbid water in the settling column and it resulted in a 91.6% reduction in turbidity (101NTU to 8.5NTU).

The results for watermelon seed extract are presented in Figures 6. The optimum dosage was 8mg/l and it resulted in about 97% reduction in turbidity (98NTU to 2.75NTU).

Figure 6. Regression Plot of Turbidity Against Watermelon Seed Extract Dosage

Table 3. Percentage Removal Efficiency (R %) as a Function of Time and Depth for M.Oleifera Seed Extract

Depth (m)	Time (min)								
	20	40	60	80	100	120	140	160	180
0.5	47	51	55	57	56	68	81	85	90
1.0	38	42	45	47	52	61	74	83	86
1.5	34	37	39	41	45	56	66	76	84
2.0	11	17	27	35	41	47	59	70	78
Average (%)	32.5	36.8	41.5	45	48.5	58	70	78.5	84.5

From Table 3, the average removal efficiency increased (from 32.5% to 84.5%) as the time increased. This is expected as the progress of time allows the formation of flocs to proceed leading to higher settlement of suspended particles [2].

STATISTICAL ANALYSIS

The analysis was carried out using one-way Analysis of Variance (ANOVA) to compare the Overall Removal Efficiency of the three coagulants. The procedure is as follows:

Null Hypothesis (H0): $\mu_1 = \mu_2 = \mu_3$; $\alpha = 0.05$ (95% confidence interval)

Alternative Hypothesis (H1): reject Ho

The results obtained are given below in Table 4.

From Table 4 the P-value (0.54) was greater than α (0.05). That is $P > \alpha$. So, we can accept the Ho hypothesis and say that there is no significant difference between the means of the three samples.

As a result of this, the sedimentation tanks can be designed for all three coagulants using the same procedure.

Table 4. Analysis of Variance Comparing the Removal Efficiencies of All Three Coagulants

Groups	Count	Sum	Average	Variance		
Watermelon Seed Extract	6	458	76.33	39.06		
Alum	6	328	54.66	62.66		
<i>Moringa oleifera</i> Seed Extract	6	570	95	13.6		
	SS	df	MS	F	P-value	F crit
Between Groups	98.11	2	49.06	0,65	0.54	3.682
Within Groups	1139	15	75.97			

CONCLUSION

- i. Clay suspension dosage (x) had a high linear correlation with turbidity (y). The relationship obtained is given by $y = 1.0705x - 9.7131$ with coefficient of variation of 0.9967 making it suitable for replicating turbidity in synthetic turbid water.
- ii. From the jar tests, the optimum dosages of the coagulants were 3mg/l, 8mg/l and 6mg/l for M.Oleifera seed extract, Watermelon seed extract and alum, respectively as coagulants.
- iii. The optimum removal efficiencies observed from the settling column tests were 99%, 84% and 65% using alum, M.Oleifera and watermelon seeds, respectively.
- iv. Finally the plant designed using M.Oleifera seed extract as coagulant was the more economical among the two bio-coagulants (3m width by 37.8m length by 2.5m depth for M.Oleifera seed and 3m wide by 48.3m length by 2.5m depth watermelon seed extract) from their dimensions. This showed that M.oleifera seed extract could be a viable alternative to alum as a coagulant used in water treatment.

RECOMMENDATIONS

The following recommendations were made for future works after the completion of this study:

- i. Further research should be carried out to study the effects of these bio-coagulants on other treatment parameters such as pH and conductivity.
- ii. Also effort should be put into utilization of M.oleifera as a coagulant in large scale water treatment facilities so as to reduce the economic strain from the high cost of procuring alum.

CONFLICT OF INTERESTS

The author declares no conflict of interests arising from this study and there are no competing interest.

APPRECIATION

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